

THE ORGANIZATION READINESS INDEX, AS A DECISION SUPPORT TOOL FOR CONSIGNMENT STOCK PROGRAM ADOPTION IN A “LEAGILE” SUPPLY CHAIN

Author(s)*: Monica FAUR¹, Constantin BUNGĂU², Florin BLAGA³, Cosmin GHERGHEA⁴, Alin POP⁵
Position: PhD Student¹, Prof. PhD², Prof. PhD³, PhD Student⁴, Lect. PhD⁵
University: University of Oradea
Address: Oradea, 1 Universitatii Str., Romania^{1,2,3,4,5}
Email: monica.faur@csud.uoradea.ro¹, bungau@uoradea.ro², florin_bлага2000@yahoo.com³,
cosmin.gherghea@gmail.com⁴, alinpop23@yahoo.com⁵
Webpage: <http://www.uoradea.ro>

Abstract

Purpose – The study proposes a decision support tool (DST) that takes into account the readiness of an organization to accept and implement a consignment stock program (CSP) adoption in a ‘leagile’ supply chain.

Methodology/approach - The paper includes a brief overview on multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) methods and uses Fuzzy logic theory to capture the uncertainty that usually occur in a decision process.

Findings – A correct and realistic decision, which is well accepted by the organization team is easier to implement and creates a sooner positive outcome.

Research limitations/implications – The proposed decisional model has a degree of limitation in the meaning that it must be adjusted according to the specific criteria of each business environment.

Practical implications – The seven steps DST was designed to assist the practitioners, in their decision making processes, and to encourage them to use multi-criteria mathematical programming in their basic activities, as it is proved to increase their efficiency.

Originality/value – The present research integrates the voices of the internal functions into a decisional process matrix. An organization readiness index is defined, to reflect the degree to which a business unit is prepared to adopt and implement a CSP.

Key words: Decision support tool, organization readiness, consignment stock

Introduction

Globalization phenomenon continues to have a growing impact on business organizations, especially on their strategies and practices. Increased competition puts more pressure on managers, forcing them to perform at higher levels and making correct decisions at the right moments. The present study represents a part of a wider research, focused on CSP adoption and implementation in a supply chain governed by lean and agile strategies.

Most of the industry players seek to improve their supply chains performance by implementing lean and agile concepts and practices, either separately, or simultaneous as a ‘leagile’ hybrid system (Faur & Bungău, 2018). Lean management is the provision of maximum customer satisfaction by reducing waste through optimum utilization of resources (Womack & Jones, 2003; Gherghea & Bungău, 2018; Gherghea, Bungău & Negrău, 2019), while agile concept requires provisional sources of supplies and employment, immediately available, to accommodate the inherent variations on the market (Faur & Bungău, 2019b).

An effective supply chain management, by adopting the most appropriate strategies in a knowledge-based society, determines new approaches of conducting the business. (Abrudan & Candea, 2002; Drăghici, 2007; Avasilcăi & Rusu, 2015). These might include taking advantage of already tested models, useful programs, or best practices, along with changing the organizational culture and listening to the

voices of business functions, in order to ensure a successful implementation. Thus, having an efficient DST, pre-designed for different business models or policies is at great help and sometimes crucial. Making the good choice is of the essence when it comes to performance improvement. Under these circumstances, the present paper aims to develop a DST, with application in CSP, considering the readiness of the organization to accept the model.

Problem definition

In both, literature and practice, CSP is known as an appropriate solution towards reducing inventory cost, as well as eliminating shortages, forecast accuracy issues and bringing procurement lead-times to zero, all of these being essential objectives in supply chain management. The consigned materials are legally owned by the supplier, but held by the buyer, so there are no financial implications for the buyer until the materials are consumed. The fundamentals of CSP are explained in Valentini & Zavanella, (2003). However, it is important for the organization to be ready to adopt such initiatives. A research and a case study presented by Faur & Bungău, (2019a) demonstrated that a 'leagile' company, already having in place streamline processes, clearly defined and allocated responsibilities, along with a robust ERP software solution (e.g. SAP), is more prepared to adapt to this kind of changes and has a higher rate of a success in implementation than a common firm. Nevertheless, this is not a sufficient condition, as the same authors showed that a positive result is not warranted for another subsidiary of the same company, acting under the same rules and strategies, but where the idea of adopting the CSP generated mass resistance and real barriers to the project implementation. The problems have been addressed by investigating and assessing the risks associated with the challenges, and a solution framework has been proposed, in order to overcome the barriers towards achieving the benefits of the CSP (Faur et al, 2020). The result demonstrated that people perception can be changed when the issues are properly addressed, information is shared and specific solutions are provided. Based on these insights, the present study intends to continue the research in this area by developing a decision model which integrates among the decision criteria the voices of the internal functions, making them allies in the process of change, instead of generating conflicts.

Research methodology

The study includes a brief overview on MCDM methods and proposes a DSP for CSP adoption in a 'leagile' supply chain. Fuzzy logic theory is used to capture the uncertainty and doubt that usually occur in a decisional process. The objective is to enhance the effectiveness of a decision making process and consequently to identify the appropriate criteria, rank them according to their level of importance, to the priorities and interrelations, then obtain the most suitable combination, in alignment with the real situation. Numerical examples are considered to validate the proposed model and further, an index of organization readiness is defined, in accordance with the result obtained for the focal company.

Overview of various multi-criteria decision making methods

There are multiple studies and surveys concerning fuzzy MCDM, which classify the contributions in the field depending on the theoretical basis used for the modeling. Chen & Hwan, (1992) consider that there are fuzzy ranking methods (e.g. fuzzy mean and spread, centroid index, linguistic ranking methods) and fuzzy multiple attribute decision making methods, including fuzzy simple additive weighting methods, analytic hierarchy process (AHP), fuzzy outranking methods, or maximin methods (Carlsson & Fuller, 1996). There are also main contributions in fuzzy mathematical programming, subject that is in detail presented by Inuiguchi, Ichihashi & Tanaka, (1990) in their survey.

Fuzzy MCDM models are meant to sort different options according to predetermined criteria with a single decision-maker or through group decision-making (Sofuoglu, 2019). Initially, MCDM methods assumed that all the criteria were independent, then, gradually, conflicts were introduced due to the necessity to represent antagonist interests of the decision-making group members and new methods have been developed to consider interdependent criteria (Yager, 1994).

In order to enhance precision in the results, several researchers used in their studies combinations of different methods. For example, Hsu, (2003) suggested a multi-criteria approach to integrate different opinions into an AHP, combined with the utilization of fuzzy numbers (Hsu et al, 2003), while Zhu, (2015) proposed to use evidential reasoning rules, which is another multi-criteria approach, in order to overcome the limitations of simple additive methods (Zhu et al, 2015).

Mamdani and Tagaki-Sugeno Fuzzy Inference Systems (FIS) are two widely-applied MCDM methods. The key difference between these two FIS techniques is the manner in which they calculate their crisp output values. The Mamdani-type FIS requires defuzzification, whereas the Tagaki-Sugeno-type FIS applies a constant weighted-average technique avoiding defuzzification (Khosravanian et al, 2016). Table 1 presents a number of differences among Fuzzy Mamdani and Fuzzy Tagaki-Sugeno.

Table 1. Differences among Fuzzy Mamdani and Tagaki-Sugeno (adapted from Khosravanian et al, 2016)

FIS Type	Mamdani	Tagaki -Sugeno
Fuzzification	Singleton	Singleton
Inference process	Min-max	Min-product; Order 0
Defuzzification	Center of gravity	Weighted average
Rule format	IF x and/or y, rule strength, THEN z	F x is A and y is B THEN Z = f(x,y)

Developing the DST

As mentioned in the 'Problem definition' section, the present study is based on the insights from a couple of other previous exploratory cases of CSP implementation, one of them being successful and the other one having a negative outcome in the first attempt. Mamdani-type FIS, introduced in 1975 by Ebrahim Mamdani, was chosen to develop the DST. The decision criteria and the membership rules are set with the involvement of the stakeholders impacted by the CSP, who are included in the decision process along with the project team. The criteria include the benefits and costs along with organizational capabilities, suppliers' reliability, constraints and perceived risks. The latter criteria act like perturbation factors in the decision making process, increasing the uncertainty and level of fuzziness. Scores among the criteria were obtained based on expert interviews and a survey addressed to the stakeholders. The decision input and output variables are detailed in table 2, along with the assigned weighting for each criterion, the allocated ranges, linguistic degrees and inference rules that have been agreed.

Table 2. Decision input and output variables, weighting, rules, and linguistic degrees

Main criteria groups (set as output variables)	Crit. No.	Notations	Decision criteria (set as input variables)	Crit. Weight (%)	Input variable - range	Rules and linguistic degrees	Output variable - range [0-1]
Benefits and costs	1	Benefits	Lower average monthly inventory value (AMIV) for the consigned materials versus actual with 10%-50%	35	[10%-50%]	AMIV=50%decrease= Very High=>Decision=Yes [0.8-1] AMIV=40%decrease= High =>D=Probably Yes [0.6-0.8] AMIV=30%decrease=Med=> D=Almost Yes[0.4-0.6] AMIV=20%decrease=Low=> D=Almost No[0.2-0.4] AMIV=10%decrease=Very Low=>D=N [0-0.2]	Very low Low Medium High Very high

Main criteria groups (set as output variables)	Crit. No.	Notations	Decision criteria (set as input variables)	Crit. Weight (%)	Input variable - range	Rules and linguistic degrees	Output variable - range [0-1]
	2	Costs	Costs related to extra FTE full-time equivalent), training for new competences, new SAP CS module & extra storage space	15	[3000-10000] Eur	very low ≤ 3000 ; D=Yes[0.8-1] low-3001-5000 [0.6-0.8] medium-5001-7000 [0.4-0.6] High-7001-8500 [0.2-0.4] Very High-8501-10000 [0-0.2]	
Organization capabilities & suppliers' reliability	3	SSC	Storage space capacity for the consigned materials (SSC) Actual = 400sqm - CSP optimum=700sqm	15	[400-700] sqm	Equal actual=400sqm=> D=No[0-0.4] Acceptable=500sqm=>D= Probably Yes [0.4-0.5] Required=600sqm=> D=Almost Yes[0.4-0.7] Optimum=700sqm; D=Yes[0.7-1]	Less good Acceptable Good Very good Almost perfect
	4	IIS	Integrated information systems with suppliers; SAP compatible systems	5	[1-10]	Very less compatible; No[0-0.2] Less compatible; Probably Yes [0.1-0.3] Relative compatible; Yes [0.2-0.5] Compatible; Ye [0.4-0.7] Very compatible; Yes[0.7-1]	
	5	RS	Reliable suppliers (RS), upon an internal evaluation of the embedded suppliers	10	[1-10]	Very Less reliable; No[0-0.2] Less reliable; Probably Yes [0.1-0.3] Relative reliable; Yes [0.2-0.5] Reliable; Yes [0.4-0.7] Very reliable; Yes[0.7-1]	
Functions voices integration: acceptance level of perceived risks (ALPR)	6	PR	Perceived risks (PR)	12	[10-100]	PR=Very low => D=Yes[0.8-1] PR=Low; D=Almost Yes[0.7-0.8] PR=Medium=>D=Probably Yes [0.6-0.7] PR=High=>D= Probably No [0.3-0.5] PR=Very High=>D=No [0-0.3]	Very low Low Medium High Very High
	7	IC	Implementation complexity (IC)	8	[1-10]	IC=Low=>D=Yes[0.8-1] IC=Medium=>D= Probably Yes [0.4-0.9] IC=High=>D=No [0-0.5]	
				100			

The Mamdani inference process is developed in five stages: fuzzification of crisp input values, application of logical operators in the antecedent of each rule, implication to the consequent of each rule, aggregation of the consequents of all the rules and defuzzification of the final aggregate (Chen and Klein, 1997). The result, a number, is a centroid of area, or in other words a center-of-gravity, reflecting the combination of all the input variables according to the given set of rules. Based on the FIS principles and the key actions that have to be performed, a seven steps DST proposal is developed by the authors (figure 1).

The DST refers to the action plan, namely the successive steps which are aligned with the supporting Mamdani FIS and which are compulsory to follow, in order to evaluate the organization readiness to adopt CSP and get a final decision. Upon defining relevant criteria, they are organized in pairs or triad groups, and then a process of mapping the input data sets into outputs is carried out, using fuzzy logic approach. Then, by concatenating the partial results and using the weighted arithmetic mean, the organization readiness index (IOR) is determined.

Figure 1. The proposed DST in seven steps

Results and discussions

The inference system or the decision-making unit performs the inference operations on the rules and in the way the rules are combined, expressing the potential assessment of the constituent subsystems. Once the consensus is reached on the definition of variables and the decision rules, the inference process can be initiated for each criteria group. The implementation was developed with the “Fuzzy” toolbox of MATLAB software. Some of the sequential results are presented in figures 2-5.

Figure 2. Input and output members for group 'Organizational capabilities & suppliers' reliability'

Decision-making with interdependent multiple criteria is a quite difficult task using traditional means. In case of conflicting objectives there normally is no optimal solution which would simultaneously satisfy all the criteria. On the flip side, if we have pairwise supportive parameters, that positively influence one another, then this attribute should be maximized to find the synergistic effect and Mandami FIS has the ability to integrate such circumstances.

Figure 3. Rule viewer for Organizational capabilities: a suitable output value = 0.788

Figure 4. Inference maps for different criteria combinations: (a) supportive criteria; (b) conflicting; (c) – quite equivalent

Figure 5. Agreed rules for 'Organizational capabilities' group of criteria

The developed model was tested in order to verify if it simulates the real situations described by dataset. The results indicate that the selected variables provide suitable values in the direction of adopting CSP. It also provides clear guidance in respect of what parameters have to be improved, or which of them can act as limitations, just by a simple movement of a gridline. The final results are obtained after several iterations and adjustments of variables ranges in order to get a suitable scenario. Figure 6 shows the final IOR, together with the output results per groups, and their weighting in the decisional process.

Figure 6. Weighted index IOR

Conclusions

In several cases the decisions taken by the top management are only considered from the perspective of business performance, but often the projects fail upon or during implementation, because they are difficult to be accepted by the stakeholders. The present research takes into account as a decision input variable, the voices of the internal functions, through their perceived risks, and as an output, the accepted level of the perceived risks. This approach will lead to a correct decision, which might be well accepted by the organization team, and consequently generating a sooner positive outcome upon implementation.

The seven steps DST proposal is designed to assist the practitioners in their decision making process, while it also contributes to the existing literature in the field of CSP adoption.

Mamdani FIS was a useful approach to determine the IOR, which reflects the degree to which an organization is prepared to adopt and implement a new project.

Future research objectives might focus on using other fuzzy logic MCDM, or combination of different methods to find an enhanced alternative to our DST, in terms of precision and efficiency.

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